

European Nucleotide Archive

Genome Assemblies and Annotation Data Submission

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ENA Background: What is ENA?

Open platform for the management, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data

- **Globally comprehensive scientific record** and European node of **INSDC**
- **Broad scope** covering raw data, through layers of interpretation and context
- **Connectivity** with broader EMBL-EBI resources
- Sequence data **foundation**
- Rich submission, discovery and retrieval **software, tools and services**
- **Support** through Helpdesk and training
- **Management**, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data
- **Data coordination** including project-specific data hubs and portals

Archive

Platform

Data sharing

Why is it important to share data?

- Findability
- Accessibility
- Interoperability
- Reproducibility/Reusability
- Data standards
- Community collaboration

Maximum value

Submitting data to the ENA

All data in the ENA is submitted by members of the research community

What motivates people to submit?

- Open data
- Reproducibility
- Reusability
- 3rd party access
- Archival
- **Publication**
- Downstream analyses

*The data lifecycle, from ELIXIR Europe
<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>*

Data resources at EMBL-EBI

ENA - an ELIXIR Core Data Resource

- The ENA is part of the wider ecosystem of biodata resources
- Recognised as an ELIXIR CDR and Global Core Biodata Resource by the Global Biodata Coalition
- Integration into a system of biodata resources increases value in genomics data

GLOBAL
CORE
BIODATA
RESOURCE

Data Structure at ENA

ENA Data Structure

- ENA stores huge amounts of data
 - ... from many users
 - ... with samples from many taxa
 - ... who use many different techniques
 - ... and sequence on many different platforms
- But we need to display data in a consistent manner
- A robust model is the first step in achieving this

ENA Data model

Sequence data is organised into tiers:

- **Reads:** raw sequence data
- **Assemblies:** reconstructions of actual replicons
- **Annotations:** interpretations of biological function

Annotation and **assembly** are frequently paired

ENA Metadata Model

- Data without any context has no value
- Metadata tells us how sequence data was produced
- Makes it possible to compare datasets:

“I want to see data from insects...

... collected in Argentina ...

... sampled above 1000m ...

... between April and June ...

... compared with the same in Costa Rica”

- Archives have spent a lot of time thinking about this!

ENA Metadata Model: Study

Podarcis lilfordi is an emblematic Mediterranean lizard of the Balearic Islands.

Due to its large phenotypic diversity this species is a great model system for evolutionary studies in insular ecosystems and a challenging target for conservation.

The authors published the first high-quality chromosome level assembly and its annotation.

Gomez-Garrido et al, DNA Research (2023), doi.org/10.1093/dnares/dsad008

ENA Metadata Model: Study

Bioproject structure

- direct link from the species project
- links from umbrella projects to ERGA
- links from umbrella projects to EBP

Umbrella projects

Hierarchical bioproject structure

Project: PRJEB50294

This project collects the sequencing data and assemblies generated for *Podarcis lilfordi* by the Catalan Initiative for the Earth Biogenome Project (<https://www.biogenoma.cat>).

Study Title: Podarcis lilfordi
Center Name: Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico;UB (Universitat de Barcelona)
Broker Name: CNAG-CRG
Keyword: CBP
ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2022-03-31
ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2022-06-27

Component Projects

Accession	Title/Description
PRJEB50058	Podarcis lilfordi (Lilford's wall lizard), genomic data. This project collects the genomic data generated for Podarcis lilfordi, common name Lilford's wall l... See more
PRJEB47961	Podarcis lilfordi (Lilford's wall lizard), genome assembly, rPodLi1 This project provides the genome assembly of Podarcis lilfordi, common name Lilford's wall lizard. T... See more

Data projects

ENA Metadata Model: Study


```

<PROJECT_SET>
  <PROJECT accession="PRJEB50294" alias="rPodLil1" broker_name="Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico">
    <IDENTIFIERS>
      <PRIMARY_ID>PRJEB50294</PRIMARY_ID>
      <SUBMITTER_ID namespace="Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico">rPodLil1</SUBMITTER_ID>
    </IDENTIFIERS>
    <TITLE>Podarcis lilfordi</TITLE>
    <DESCRIPTION>This project collects the sequencing data and assemblies generated by this project</DESCRIPTION>
    <UMBRELLA_PROJECT/>
    <RELATED_PROJECTS>
      <RELATED_PROJECT>
        <CHILD_PROJECT accession="PRJEB47961"/>
      </RELATED_PROJECT>
      <RELATED_PROJECT>
        <CHILD_PROJECT accession="PRJEB50058"/>
      </RELATED_PROJECT>
      <RELATED_PROJECT>
        <PARENT_PROJECT accession="PRJEB49670"/>
      </RELATED_PROJECT>
    </RELATED_PROJECTS>
    <PROJECT_LINKS>
      <PROJECT_LINK>
        <XREF_LINK>
          <DB>ENA-SUBMISSION</DB>
          <ID>ERA8435046</ID>
        </XREF_LINK>
      </PROJECT_LINK>
    </PROJECT_LINKS>
  </PROJECT>
</PROJECT_SET>
  
```

ENA Metadata Model: Sample

ENA Metadata Model: Sample

By Orchi - Self-photographed, CC BY-SA 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=890856>

The authors collected five adult species of *Podarcis lilfordi* under national permits.

A female adult specimen was chosen for genome sequencing.

Gomez-Garrido et al, DNA Research (2023),
doi.org/10.1093/dnares/dsad008

Biosample structure

Biosample relations in complex datasets

ENA Metadata Model: Sample

1 specimen and 3 samples registered for the organism

Biosample: [SAMEA9991229](#)

Podarcis lilfordi kidney DNA

Organism:	Podarcis lilfordi
Scientific Name:	Podarcis lilfordi
Sample Accession:	SAMEA9991229
Location:	39.801159 N 4.290024 E
Center Name:	UB (Universitat de Barcelona)
Sample Alias:	rPodLi1_2
Checklist:	ERC000053
Broker Name:	CNAG-CRG
Sample Title:	Podarcis lilfordi kidney DNA
Geographic Location (Depth):	0
Original Collection Date:	2021-04-21
Habitat:	island
Collection Date:	2021-04-24
Sample Derived From:	ERS9986629
Geographic Location (Longitude):	4.290024

ENA Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

Minimum amount of information expected to describe biological samples required for registration in ENA

Sample Checklists

There is a minimum amount of information required during ENA sample registration and all samples must conform to a defined checklist of expected metadata values. The most suitable checklist for sample registration depends on the type of the sample.

These sample checklists have been developed to meet the needs of different research communities. Different communities have different requirements on the minimum metadata expected to describe biological samples. For any questions regarding checklists, contact us [here](#).

Filter by accession/name/description/field name

Accession	Name	Description
ERC000050	ENA binned metagenome	Minimum information to standardise metadata of binned metagenome samples. Ensures binned and MAG metagenome assembly metadata is compatible.
ERC000051	PDX Checklist	Minimum information required for reporting samples associated with patient-derived xenograft (PDX) models or patient samples
ERC000052	HoloFood Checklist	Minimum information required for reporting HoloFood samples. HoloFood is a 'hologenomic' approach that will improve the efficiency of food production systems by understanding the biomolecular and physiological processes affected by incorporating feed additives and novel sustainable feeds in farmed animals (https://www.holofood.eu/).
ERC000053	Tree of Life Checklist	Minimum information required for reporting samples associated with the Tree of Life Programme (https://www.sanger.ac.uk/programme/tree-of-life/).
ERC000055	GSC MixS agriculture	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.

ENA Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

- ENA metadata checklists guided by standards working groups and the communities
 - Keep up with requirements within communities
- Rich standardised metadata facilitates linking to source information
- General minimum requirements (INSDC)
 - Organism information mandatory and linked with NCBI taxonomy
 - INSDC spatiotemporal policy: mandatory provision of collection date & geographic location
 - INSDC missing value reporting

INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update (03-03-2023)

[Home](#) > [News & Announcements](#) > [INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update \(03-03-2023\)](#)

INSDC continues its aim to increase the number of sequences for which the origin of the sample can be precisely located in time and space through harmonisation of accurate geographical annotation and date and time of collection information.

ENA Metadata Model: Tree of Life Checklist

You have selected **Tree of Life Checklist**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Comprehensive sample checklist developed with the community for Tree of Life samples

Add custom field

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	tax_id	Text field	None	Taxonomy ID of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database . Entries in the NCBI Taxonomy database have integer taxon IDs. See our tips for sample taxonomy here
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	scientific_name	Text field	None	Scientific name of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database . Scientific names typically follow the binomial nomenclature. For example, the scientific name for humans is Homo sapiens.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_alias	Text field	None	Unique name of the sample. If not selected system will auto generate an unique alias
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_title	Text field	None	Title of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_description	Text field	None	Description of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	organism part	Text field	None	The part of organism's anatomy or substance arising from an organism from which the biomaterial was derived, excludes cells.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	lifestage	<input type="text" value="Permitted values"/>	None	the age class or life stage of the organism at the time of collection.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	project name	Text field	None	Name of the project within which the sequencing was organized

ENA Metadata Model: Tree of Life Checklist

You have selected **Tree of Life Checklist**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Mandatory Fields

Recommended Fields

Optional Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	Latitude Start	Regular expression	DD	Latitude of the location where the sampling event started, e.g. each CTD cast, net tow, or bucket collection is a distinct event. Format: ##.####, Decimal degrees; North= +, South= -; Use WGS 84 for GPS data. Example: -24.6666.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Longitude Start	Regular expression	DD	Longitude of the location where the sampling event started, e.g. each CTD cast, net tow, or bucket collection is a distinct event. Format: ###.####, Decimal degrees; East= +, West= -; Use WGS 84 for GPS data. Example: -096.1012.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Latitude End	Regular expression	DD	Latitude of the location where the sampling event ended, e.g. each CTD cast, net tow, or bucket collection is a distinct event. Format: ##.####, Decimal degrees; North= +, South= -; Use WGS 84 for GPS data. Example: -24.6643.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Longitude End	Regular expression	DD	Longitude of the location where the sampling event ended, e.g. each CTD cast, net tow, or bucket collection is a distinct event. Format: ###.####, Decimal degrees; East= +, West= -; Use WGS 84 for GPS data. Example: -096.1171.
<input type="checkbox"/>	relationship	Text field	None	indicates if the specimen has a known relationship to another specimen (e.g. parental, child, sibling or other kind of relationship)
<input type="checkbox"/>	reference to host sample from ambient	Text field	None	Reference to host sample from ambient. The referenced sample should already

ENA Metadata Model: Experiment

ENA Metadata Model: Experiment

High molecular weight DNA was extracted from the samples.

Genome sequencing was performed using short reads (Illumina NovaSeq 6000), long reads (ONT) and Hi-C for chromosome-level scaffolding.

RNA was extracted from different tissues and the transcriptome was sequenced using Illumina NovaSeq 6000 and PacBio Iso-Seq.

ENA Metadata Model: Experiment

ENA Metadata Model: Run

ENA Metadata Model: Run

The 20 experiments hold either pairs of fastq files, or bam files or fast5.

These are compressed and uploaded to a database, where they undergo processing and wait to be made public.

```
@SRR2960126.1 1/1
GCCAGCTATATCAGTTTCCTTTGTGATGGGGCGTTTATGTAAGGGATGGGTATGGAACGCACCCTGGCTAGAACGAAAAGACTTGCTAT
TGTGAAGTTA
+
=;?AD=D?FDB??ACGHGGEHCEEHC@GDG>GDGHFF@9?C<38BFEACHIID>EEC>A3@D;?=:ABCA?
@@A8=B=B>89>ACCCACCADC3@4@@A
@SRR2960126.2 2/1
GTGGGTAACATTTGGAACAGAAAAACAAAAGTAGAATGGTGGGTGAGGAGAACAATAAAAATGATACTTCATTTAATTATCATTTAGA
GATGATATC
+
CCCFDFFHHHHIJIJJJJJJJJJJJI?
DGIJJJBFHIFGGGIJIJJJJHHHHFFFFFFFDEEEEDFEDEEEEDDDDDDEEFFDD
@SRR2960126.3 3/1
CTTTTAAACAAGATTTTTTAAAAAATGCTGTGCTGTAATCACTAGCAAAAACCTAATTTGCTAGTTGCATTGGAAGATATTGATACT
TGACAATTTA
+
CCCCFFFFHDDFFGHHHJIIJJIIJJJJIIJIGHIIJJJJIIJJJJJJJJJJIGJIHGHHHFFFFFFFEDCCACDDEEEDDD
DDDDDDDDDD
@SRR2960126.4 4/1
GCTTTTTTTCGGCAACGATGGAATCGATCAATTGTTATTGTGACAGCTAAATTGATAAAACAAAATGATACAGTTTCAAACGATCAAAA
ATTTGCAGCA
+
@=?DDDBDFBHD<FBHAHBD@FGIEDHGH?BB9BFGHIDF@===FCGEGGGH3AEHC;@DDF@C>;A@AC:
5-5;>@C@CCC::@ACBA@C:4>:(2
```

ENA Metadata Model: Run

Metadata Model: Read Submission Checklist

You have selected **Fastq File Type**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Show Description

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Field Label	Permitted Value	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample	Sample		Sample alias or accession.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	study	Study		Study alias or accession.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	instrument_model	Instrument model	Permitted values	The sequencing instrument model used in the experiment
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_name	Library name		The name for the library if any.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_source	Library source	Permitted values	The type of source material that is being sequenced.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_selection	Library selection	Permitted values	The method used to select for or against, enrich, or screen the material being sequenced.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_strategy	Library strategy	Permitted values	The sequencing technique intended for this library.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_layout	Library layout	Permitted values	The library layout specifies whether to expect single or paired configuration of reads.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	forward_file_name	Forward file name		Please enter compressed fastq the file name including any subdirectory name
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	forward_file_md5	Forward File checksum		The file MD5 checksum. This field is mandatory if you do not use the Webin File Uploader or upload the checksum using a .md5 file.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reverse_file_name	Reverse file name		Please enter compressed fastq the file name including any subdirectory name
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reverse_file_md5	Reverse file checksum		The file MD5 checksum. This field is mandatory if you do not use the Webin File Uploader or upload the checksum using a .md5 file.

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

```
>ENA|PEHZ01000001|PEHZ01000001.1 Insect metagenome contig_0_374_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GATACGTTGTCAGGTGCAAGGGTATGTGCATGGAGGGGTGCGTGTATAGGTGCGAGGATG
TGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGGAAGTGTGTGTGCATGGAGGATACGTGTGCAGGTGCAAGGGTA
TGTGCATGGAGGGGTGCGTGTATAGTCCGAGGATGTGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTAGGGT
GTGTGTAGGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTGAGTGTGTATGTGCATGGAGGGGTGTCAGGTGCAA
GGGTATGTGCATGGAGGGGTGCGTGTATAGGTGCGAGGATGTGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTG
AGGGTGTGTGTAGGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTGAGTGTGTATGTGCATGGAGGGGTGTCAGG
TGCAAGGGTATGTG
>ENA|PEHZ01000002|PEHZ01000002.1 Insect metagenome contig_2_497_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACATACTAGGGTAAAATACCCTAAAGTAGAAGCAAAAGTTA
ATATATTAACGCATAACTATGAGATACTATTTCTCTGTATGAAAATGATTAAGGATTAG
TATGAGAATCTACGGGTTTTCTATTTTCATCTGAGTTTATGCTGGAGTCTATTATATCTA
TTTTAACGAGAATAAAGAAACCTAGATACTTTTATAACACAAAGAGATATTAACAATTT
CTATTCACGTTTTATTTAGTAGGTATGAATTAAGAACTATCTAAGATTCAATTAATTCAT
AATGAAAGAAAATGAATGGTTAGAAAAAGAAAATAAAAACTTTCATTTACTTCTAGAATC
TGGTAGTAACCTAATAGAGATGATAATTTGATTTATCATGCCAAAGATTATAGCGGAGTT
AAAAATAGTGAAGTAAAAATTGACCAGTTTTGAGTGGAGGTCGCTAGATGGTCCGGGTAGGTG
GAGGTCGCTAGATGGTC
>ENA|PEHZ01000003|PEHZ01000003.1 Insect metagenome contig_4_469_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACATCATTGCGCTAAATGCAAGTTCGGATGCTGTTTGGACTT
TTCCATGAAGTGATGTTTCTCCATCATCGACAGTCAATGTTGTACGCGAATCAGGAATC
GTAGTCGATTGACTCACCGAGTCATCATCGGGCTGACTGTGCGATGAACAAATCGTG
TCTGATGCATGAAAGGTACTGGGCCAATTTGTGCGACGAAATTTGAAAAGTACGGCGTACC
TCAGGAATCATCGGTGTGGGAACTTTGTAAAAATCAGTGTGTCATTTATCAAGACAGCT
TTGAAAGGGCGCCATCGCGCCAGGGTCTTTAAGCTCAGTATTTGCCACAGTATCAGAA
AACCGGCAACTAAACAGACCCGTCGCGTTTGAATAATCCTTCCAAACAGGCCCTT
CTTCGTCATTTGATCGAAATGGGGCTGGTGGAGGTCGCTAGATGGTC
>ENA|PEHZ01000004|PEHZ01000004.1 Insect metagenome contig_8_628_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACTCAAACCTCCAGGGTATTTGCTAGCTCAAAAATACCCAC
TATCGCTATCGTAATGAATTTCTATCTTGAATCTCACTACCTGGTTTTTCAGCGCGTTTAA
```

Read data generated was assembled following the workflow described in the publication.

The genome assembly was manually curated.

The aligned transcriptome sequenced was used to generate the genome annotation.

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

MANIFEST FILE

STUDY	ERP54321
SAMPLE	ERS12345
ASSEMBLYNAME	LIZARD_V2
ASSEMBLY_TYPE	clone or isolate
COVERAGE	260
PROGRAM	Falcon-Phase
PLATFORM	Illumina
MOLECULETYPE	Genomic DNA
FASTA	Lizard_Seq.embl.gz
CHROMOSOME_LIST	Lizard_chromosome_list.txt.gz

CHROMOSOME LIST FILE

Chr01	1	Linear-Chromosome
Chr02	2	Linear-Chromosome
Chr03	3	Linear-Chromosome
Chr04	4	Linear-Chromosome
Chr05	5	Linear-Chromosome
Chr06	6	Linear-Chromosome
Chr07	7	Linear-Chromosome
Chr08	8	Linear-Chromosome
Chr0	0	multipartite

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Navigate around the object

Project description and metadata

Project: PRJEB50058 ?

This project collects the genomic data generated for Podarcis lilfordi, common name Lilford's wall lizard, to facilitate genome assembly and annotation as part of the Catalan Initiative for the Earth Biogenome Project (<https://www.biogenoma.cat/>).

Secondary Study Accession: ERP134611

Study Title: Podarcis lilfordi (Lilford's wall lizard), genomic data.

Center Name: Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico;UB (Universitat de Barcelona)

Study Name: rPodLil

Broker Name: CNAG-CRG

Keyword: CBP

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2022-07-05

ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2023-01-13

Read Files ?

Show Column Selection ▼

Download report: JSON TSV Get download script Download selected files

[Download All](#)

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Experiment Accession	Run Accession	Tax Id	Scientific Name	Generated FASTQ files: FTP
PRJEB50058	SAMEA9991229	ERX7620480	ERR8053759	74358	Podarcis lilfordi	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR8053759.fastq.gz
PRJEB50058	SAMEA12383576	ERX7620483	ERR8053762	74358	Podarcis lilfordi	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR8053762.fastq.gz

Run-centric data table

General

View: XML
XML (STUDY)

Download: XML
XML (STUDY)

Cross References: Show

Parent Projects: Show

ORCID Data Claims: Show

Related ENA Records: Show

Data

Read Files: Hide

Navigate on data

Information for a single run

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/en/browser/home>

ENA Metadata Model: Navigation Bar

- View project metadata
- Show/hide different information about project
- Explore cross-references related to project
- Explore reads/analyses files

General

View: XML
XML (STUDY)

Download: XML
XML (STUDY)

Cross References: Show

Parent Projects: Show

ORCID Data Claims: Show

Related ENA Records: Show

Data

Read Files: Hide

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Project: PRJEB50058

This project collects the genomic data generated for *Podarcis lilfordi*, common name Lilford's wall lizard, to facilitate genome assembly and annotation as part of the Catalan Initiative for the Earth Biogenome Project (<https://www.biogenoma.cat/>).

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Center Name:	Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico;UB (Universitat de Barcelona)
Study Name:	rPodLil
Broker Name:	CNAG-CRG
Keyword:	CBP
ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC:	2022-07-05
ENA-LAST-UPDATE:	2023-01-13

Related ENA Records

Result	Count
Experiment	20
Run	20

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Experiment: ERX7624503

Illumina NovaSeq 6000 paired end sequencing

Organism: Podarcis liifordi
Experiment Accession: ERX7624503
Instrument Platform: ILLUMINA
Instrument Model: Illumina NovaSeq 6000
Center Name: Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico;UB (Universitat de Barcelona)
Library Layout: PAIRED
Library Strategy: HI-C
Library Source: GENOMIC
Library Name: Lizard_485_omniC_2
Library Selection: RANDOM

Show More

Read Files

Show Column Selection

Download report: JSON TSV

Get download script

Download selected files

Download All

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Experiment Accession	Run Accession	Tax Id	Scientific Name	Generated FASTQ files:
PRJEB50058	SAMEA9991228	ERX7624503	ERR8057782	74358	Podarcis liifordi	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR8057782_1.fastq.gz <input type="checkbox"/> All <input type="checkbox"/> ERR8057782_2.fastq.gz <input type="checkbox"/> All

General

View: XML
Download: XML
Cross References: Show
ORCID Data Claims: Show

Data

Read Files: Hide

Tags

environment by geolocation

terrestrial

New tags feature

Annotations of ENA objects

Controlled textual annotations provided to metadata objects to facilitate search and filtering

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Project: PRJEB47961

This project provides the genome assembly of Podarcis lilfordi, common name Lilford's wall lizard. The assembly is provided by the Catalan Initiative for the Earth Biogenome Project (<https://www.biogenoma.cat/>).

Assembly: GCA_947686815.1

This project provides the genome assembly of Podarcis lilfordi, common name Lilford's wall lizard. The assembly is provided by the Catalan Initiative for the Earth Biogenome Project (<https://www.biogenoma.cat/>).

Secondary Study Accession: ERP132268
Study Title: Podarcis lilfordi (Lilford's wall lizard), genome assembly, rPodLil1
Center Name: Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico, UB (Universitat de Barcelona)
Study Name: rPodLil
Broker Name: CNAG-CRG
Keyword: CBP
ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2022-11-30
ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2022-12-20

Organism: [Podarcis lilfordi](#)
Assembly Name: rPodLil1.2
Assembly Title: rPodLil1.2 assembly for Podarcis lilfordi
Assembly Level: chromosome
Genome Representation: full
Accession: GCA_947686815
Total Length: 1460103102
Ungapped Length: 1459843833
N50: 89641981
Spanned Gaps: 2321

Show More

Related ENA Records

Result	Count
Coding	38622
Assembly	1
Genome assembly contig set	1
Non-coding	45142
Sequence	21

Chromosomes

Download Script For All Records [FASTA](#) [EMBL](#)

Name	Type	Accession	Count	Download Script
1	Chromosome	OX395126.1 14 sequences from set CANTUW01	15	FASTA EMBL
2	Chromosome	OX395127.1 8 sequences from set CANTUW01	9	FASTA EMBL
3	Chromosome	OX395128.1 5 sequences from set CANTUW01	6	FASTA EMBL
4	Chromosome	OX395129.1 5 sequences from set CANTUW01	6	FASTA EMBL

ENA Metadata Model: Other features

Linking with external resources - the importance of Persistent Identifiers

Biosample: SAMN26894057 [↗](#)

Liver sample from a male adult *Callipepla californica*

Organism: *Callipepla californica brunnescens*

Scientific Name: *Callipepla californica brunnescens*

Sample Accession: SAMN26894057

Location: 39.08005 N 123.0891 W

Center Name: UCLA

Sample Alias: CC4441

Broker Name: NCBI

Sample Title: Liver sample from a male adult *Callipepla californica*

Collection Date: 2020-10-13

Secondary Accession: SRS13350135

Sub Species: brunnescens

Sex: male

Tissue: liver

Collected By: Carla Cicero

Sample Type: specimen

Specimen Voucher: MVZ:Bird:193975

Isolate: MVZ:Bird:193975

Geo Loc Name: USA: Cow Mountains Rec

Ecotype: not collected

Lat Lon: 39.08005 N 123.0891 W

Age: adult

Arctos Collaborative Collection Management Solution

Bird Collection - MUSEUM OF VERTEBRATE ZOOLOGY

Identifications

Attribute	Value	Determiner/Method/Date	Remark
Identification confidence	medium		
Nature of identification	geographic distribution		

Agents

File	Agent	Remark
collector	Carla Cicero	
collector	Thomas K Studley	

Identifiers and Relationships

Identifier	IssuedBy	Type	Collector Number
4441		collector number	

Occurrence

Term	Interpreted	Original	Remarks
Catalogue number	MVZ:Bird:193975	MVZ:Bird:193975	
Establishment events			Excluded
Occurrence ID	http://arctos.dat...3975?seid=5300976	http://arctos.dat...3975?seid=5300976	
Occurrence status	PRESENT		Inferred

GBIF

Callipepla californica subsp. brunnescens (Ridgway, 1884)

Collected in United States of America

Animalia | Chordata | Aves | Galliformes | Odontophoridae | Callipepla | Callipepla californica

Subspecies: *Callipepla californica brunnescens* (Ridgway, 1884)

Location: North America | United States of America

Elevation: 884m

Basis of record: Preserved specimen

Organism ID: http://arctos.database.museum/guid/MVZ:Bird:193975 1 occurrence

Dataset: MVZ:Bird Collection (Arctos)

Publisher: Museum of Vertebrate Zoology

Reference: http://arctos.database.museum/guid/MVZ:Bird:193975

Issues: [\(Comment derived from coordinates\)](#)

Accession	Specimen ID	Barcode	Barcode	Barcode	Barcode	Species	Size
PRJNA834144	SAMN26894057	SRX15651220	SRR19599930	2893758		<i>Callipepla californica brunnescens</i>	4.3 GB 4.5 GB
PRJNA834144	SAMN26894057	SRX15651219	SRR19599931	2893758		<i>Callipepla californica brunnescens</i>	4.4 GB 4.7 GB
PRJNA834144	SAMN26894057	SRX15651218	SRR19599932	2893758		<i>Callipepla californica brunnescens</i>	41.0 GB

Data Submission at ENA

Data Submission at ENA

- There are three submissions routes
- *'Interactive Submission'*:
 - Use your browser to fill out web forms describing your work
- *'Programmatic Submission'*:
 - Describe your work in XML documents, submit them to us using cURL
- *'Webin-CLI'*:
 - Smart submission interface, made in-house

Data Submission: Interactive

- Register your objects using your browser
- Familiar and largely accessible
- Prepare spreadsheets for bigger submissions

ENA Webin Submissions Portal

Support Manage Account Logout

Register study (project)

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.]*
22-05-2024

Short descriptive study title*
Testing de novo mutation calling artefacts by re-sequencing single mutation accumulation

Detailed study abstract*
To test for the possibility that mutation bias results could in part be artifacts of a pooled-seedling sequencing approach, we re-sequenced entire rosettes of siblings (individual plants) of one mutation accumulation line and asked if the distribution of variation called (i.e., putative somatic mutations around transcription start and termination sites) was similar to the patterns seen with the seedling pools of the 107 individual lines described in the preceding section. Specifically, we grew 10 siblings and extracted DNA from 3-week old whole rosettes. Barcoded PCR-free libraries for

Study Name
Arabidopsis mutation accumulation

Will you provide functional genome annotation?

PubMed Citations Registration

Add PubMed Citations +

PubMedId	Title	Remove
9784120	Arabidopsis thaliana: a model plant for genome analysis.	

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Checklist	ERC000013	GSC MIXS host associated							
2	tax_id	scientific_name	sample_alias	sample_title	sample_description	sample_derived_from	collection_date	geographic_location (country and/or sea)	geographic_location (latitude)	geographic_location (longitude)
3	#units								DD	DD
4										
5										

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	FileType	fastq	Read submission file type									
2	sample	study	instrument_model	library_name	library_source	library_selection	library_strategy	library_layout	forward_file_name	forward_file_md5	reverse_file_name	reverse_file_md5
3												
4												

Data Submission: Programmatic

- Prepare an XML/JSON file describing your submission
- Send this to us via HTTPS
- Correct format for JSON/XML files important for successful submission and validation of data.

- Example cURL command:

```
curl -u username:password \  
-F "SAMPLE=@sample.xml" \  
-F "SUBMISSION=@submission.xml" \  
"https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/drop-box/submit/"
```

```
<SUBMISSION>  
  <ACTIONS>  
    <ACTION>  
      <ADD/>  
    </ACTION>  
  </ACTIONS>  
</SUBMISSION>
```

```
<SAMPLE_SET>  
<SAMPLE alias="MYS176V2" center_name="">  
  <TITLE>human gastric microbiota, mucosal</TITLE>  
  <SAMPLE_NAME>  
    <TAXON_ID>129436</TAXON_ID>  
    <SCIENTIFIC_NAME>stomach metagenome</SCIENTIFIC_NAME>  
    <COMMON_NAME></COMMON_NAME>  
  </SAMPLE_NAME>  
  <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>collection date</TAG>  
      <VALUE>2010</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>host body site</TAG>  
      <VALUE>Mucosa of stomach</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>human-associated environmental package</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human-associated</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (latitude)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>1.81</VALUE>  
      <UNITS>DD</UNITS>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (longitude)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>-78.76</VALUE>  
      <UNITS>DD</UNITS>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (country and/or sea)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>Colombia</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (region and locality)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>Tumaco</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>environment (biome)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>soast</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>project name</TAG>  
      <VALUE>test12V2</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>environment (feature)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human-associated habitat</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>environmental medium</TAG>  
      <VALUE>gastric fluid</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>broad-scale environmental context</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human gut</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>local environmental context</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human gut</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>ENA-CHECKLIST</TAG>  
      <VALUE>ERC000015</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
  </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>  
</SAMPLE>  
</SAMPLE_SET>
```


ENA - Submission Tools & Data Portals

Assembly Submission

Webin-CLI Data Submission: Webin Portal

Welcome to the Webin Submissions Portal

You can use this service for a range of submission activities as well as reports on your submissions. For help with submitting your data, including the use of this interface, please refer to our Help Guides. Please familiarise yourself with the different options available. New users are advised to take a moment to understand the interface.

•Studies tab

- Used for registering studies and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered studies

•Samples tab

- Used to register new samples, requesting taxonomy for novel/unidentified/published species and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered samples

•Raw reads/experiments tab

- Used to register runs/experiments and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered runs/experiments
- Can also be used to track run files validation/processing

•ENA Metadata Model showing data objects and data structure

Studies (Projects)

Studies Report

- + Register Samples
- + Register Novel Taxonomy
- + Submit XMLs (advanced)

Samples

Samples Report

Raw Reads (Experiments and Runs)

- Runs Report
- Run Files Report
- Run Processing Report
- Unsubmitted Files Report

Submit XMLs (advanced)

Data Analyses

Assemblies and annotated sequences must be submitted with Webin-CLI. Other analyses can be submitted as XMLs.

- + Generate Annotated Sequence Spreadsheet
- + Submit XMLs (advanced)
- Analyses Report
- Analysis File Report
- Analysis Processing Report

•Analyses tab

- Used to download annotated sequences template spreadsheet and view submitted analyses metadata.
- Can also be used to track analyses files processing.

Assembly Data Submission: Webin Account

- Each submission requires a Webin account.
- Can be created by submitting web form on the Webin Portal page.
- Requires fields such as centre name, country and user credentials.
- Fields such as centre name, contact information can be updated.
- Metagenomics consent box to allow MGnify to access and analyse metagenomic data.

Account Details

Abbreviated center name	Password
Full center name	Confirm Password
Laboratory Name	
Address	
Country	

Contact Information

Add At Least One Contact

No Sensitive Data

I confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable.

Metagenomics Consent

By keeping this box checked you give consent to the EBI MGnify team to analyse those data for which you have requested a pre-publication confidential hold. Note that the data as well as the analysis results will remain confidential until the specified release date of the associated sequencing study. If you are also requesting assembly of your data by MGnify, you also give consent to MGnify to submit these assemblies to your ENA study on your behalf. MGnify will not change any metadata or data you have already submitted but may need to perform updates to submissions performed by their team in exceptional circumstances. This service provides pre-publication state-of-the-art analysis results, along with visualisations, that you may use in subsequent publications. The service is described in <http://europepmc.org/article/MED/31696235> and we kindly request, should you use these analyses in your publications, that you cite this paper.

I give consent and confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable

Save Cancel

Assembly Data Submission: Study

- Study required for each submission at the ENA.
- Needs to be registered interactively or programmatically. Webin-CLI does not support study registration.
- Umbrella projects only submitted programmatically.
- Groups data objects under one project.
- Authority on release date of data objects linked to a study.
- Add publications and study attributes to study metadata.

Webin-CLI does not support study registration

The screenshot shows a web form for submitting a study. It is divided into several sections: 'Submission Details' with fields for 'Release date', 'Study Name', and 'Short descriptive study title'; a checkbox for 'Will you provide functional genome annotation?'; 'Detailed study abstract' with a text area; 'PubMed Citations Registration' with an 'Add PubMed Citations' button; and 'Study Attributes' with an 'Add Study Attributes' button. At the bottom right, there are 'Submit' and 'Cancel' buttons.

```
<PROJECT_SET>
  <PROJECT alias="cheddar_cheese">
    <NAME>WGS Streptomyces iranensis</NAME>
    <TITLE>Characterisation of Microbial Diversity and...</TITLE>
    <DESCRIPTION>This study aimed to characterise the interaction of microbial...</DESCRIPTION>
    <SUBMISSION_PROJECT>
      <SEQUENCING_PROJECT/>
    </SUBMISSION_PROJECT>
  </PROJECT>
</PROJECT_SET>
```

Assembly Data Submission: Samples

- Samples can be registered interactively, programmatically or with Webin-CLI.
- Programmatic submissions both in JSON or XML format
- Webin-CLI submissions in JSON format
- Range of sample checklists to choose from including Environmental, Pathogen, Plant and Marine checklists.
- Include required, recommended and mandatory metadata fields.
- Mandatory minimum metadata fields for all checklists include taxonomy information, sample details, collection dates and geographic location.

```

"sample": {
  "alias": "uniqueAlias",
  "title": "human gut microbiota, mucosal",
  "organism": {
    "taxonId": "408170"
  },
  "attributes": [
    {
      "tag": "project name",
      "value": "human gut study"
    },
    {
      "tag": "collection date",
      "value": "2010-01-20"
    },
    {
      "tag": "host body site",
      "value": "Mucosa of stomach"
    },
    {
      "tag": "human-associated environmental package",
      "value": "human-associated"
    },
    {
      "tag": "geographic location (latitude)",
      "value": "1.81",
      "unit": "DD"
    },
    {
      "tag": "geographic location (longitude)",
      "value": "-78.76",
      "unit": "DD"
    },
    {
      "tag": "geographic location (country and/or sea)",
      "value": "Colombia"
    },
    {
      "tag": "geographic location (region and locality)",
      "value": "Tumaco"
    },
    {
      "tag": "environment (biome)",
      "value": "Coast"
    },
    {
      "tag": "environment (feature)",
      "value": "human-associated habitat"
    },
    {
      "tag": "environmental medium",
      "value": "gastric fluid"
    },
    {
      "tag": "broad-scale environmental context",
      "value": "human gut"
    },
    {
      "tag": "local environmental context",
      "value": "human gut"
    },
    {
      "tag": "ena-checklist",
      "value": "ERC000013"
    }
  ]
}

```

```

{
  "study": "PRJEB12345",
  "sample": {
    {
      "alias": "sediment_sample",
      "title": "Sample derived from sediment in Antarctica",
      "organism": {
        "taxonId": "77133"
      }
    },
    "attributes": [
      {
        "tag": "collection date",
        "value": "2025-01-30"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (country and/or sea)",
        "value": "Antarctica"
      },
      . . .
    ]
  },
  "name": "ena-EXPERIMENT-TEST-28-10-2024-01:02:26:880-109",
  "platform": "ILLUMINA",
  "instrument": "Illumina MiSeq",
  "insert_size": "390",
  "libraryName": "unspecified",
  "library_source": "GENOMIC",
  "library_selection": "PCR",
  "libraryStrategy": "AMPLICON",
  "fastq": {
    "value": "test_single_run_2.fastq.gz",
    "attributes": {
      "read_type": ["single"]
    }
  }
}

```

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Checklist	ERC000013	GSC MixS host associated							
2	tax_id	scientific_name	sample_alias	sample_title	sample_description	sample derived from	collection date	geographic location (country and/or sea)	geographic location (latitude)	geographic location (longitude)
3	#units							DD		DD
4										
5										

Assembly Data Submission: Run

- Raw reads may be submitted interactively, programmatically (XML or JSON file formats) and using Webin-CLI (plain text or JSON formats)
- For interactive and programmatic submissions run files must be uploaded before submission
- Supports several file formats including Fastq, BAM, CRAM, HDF5 and FAST5 (but only BAM, CRAM and Fastq file formats are supported by Webin-CLI).
- Webin-CLI validates files before submission.
- Successful submission returns a run accession with the sequence files metadata and an experiment accession with the library metadata.

Programmatic - JSON

```
"experiment":{
  {
    "alias":"exp_amtis_religiosa",
    "centerName":"EBI",
    "title":"The IKITE project:evolution of insects",
    "study":{
      "accession":"SRP017801"
    },
    "samples":{
      {
        "accession":"SRS462875"
      }
    },
    "designDescription":"","
    "libraryDescriptor":{
      "libraryName":"unspecified",
      "libraryStrategy":"RNA-Seq",
      "librarySource":"TRANSCRIPTOMIC",
      "librarySelection":"cDNA",
      "libraryLayout":"paired"
    },
    "instrumentPlatform":"ILLUMINA",
    "instrumentModel":"Illumina HSeq 2000",
    "attributes":{
      {
        "tag":"library preparation date",
        "value":"2010-08"
      }
    }
  }
}
```

manifest.txt

```
STUDY ERP013289
SAMPLE ERS980556
NAME ena-EXPERIMENT-TEST-13-03-2025-01:02:26:880-109
INSTRUMENT Illumina MiSeq
INSERT_SIZE 390
LIBRARY_SOURCE GENOMIC
LIBRARY_SELECTION PCR
LIBRARY_STRATEGY AMPLICON
FASTQ test_single_run.fastq.gz
```

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	FileType	fastq	Read submission file type									
2	sample	study	instrument_model	library_name	library_source	library_selection	library_strategy	library_layout	forward_file_name	forward_file_md5	reverse_file_name	reverse_file_md5
3												
4												

Assembly Submission: Upload read files

- For Interactive and programmatic submissions raw read sequence files need to be uploaded to Webin account before run submission.
- Can use multiple tools to upload files using FTP or Aspera.
- Runs can be submitted after upload.

Assembly Data Submission: Assembly

- Assemblies must be submitted using Webin-CLI
- Assembly submission uses a manifest file in plain text or JSON format.
- The set of files required for submission of a genome assembly depends on the assembly level:
 - Contig assembly (default)
 - Scaffold Assembly (contigs separated by gaps of known length)
 - Chromosome Assembly
- Success submission returns an analysis accession - but not to be used for referencing an assembly in a publication
- After the submission is processed a Genome assembly accession (GCA_xxxx), and the sequence accessions are assigned, and these are sent to the submitters by email or can be retrieved from the Webin Portal or from the Webin Reports Service.

Assembly Data Submission: Assembly

Assembly Data Submission: Assembly

Manifest.txt

```
STUDY          PRJEB71679
SAMPLE         ERS123456
RUN_REF        ERR765834
ASSEMBLYNAME   barley_1
ASSEMBLY_TYPE  clone or isolate
COVERAGE       90
PROGRAM        Flye_v2.9
PLATFORM       ILLUMINA
FLATFILE       barley_1.embl.gz
CHROMOSOME_LIST  barley_1_chromosome_list.txt.gz
```

Chromosome list file

```
Chr01  1  Linear-Chromosome
Chr02  2  Linear-Chromosome
Chr03  3  Linear-Chromosome
Chr04  4  Linear-Chromosome
Chr05  5  Linear-Chromosome
Chr06  6  Linear-Chromosome
Chr07  7  Linear-Chromosome
Chr08  8  Linear-Chromosome
Chr0   0  multipartite
```

```
ID  XXX; XXX; linear; genomic DNA; XXX; XXX; XXX.
XX
AC  XXX;
XX
AC  * _contig_1
XX
PR  Project:PRJEB71679;
XX
DT  13-JAN-2024 (Rel. 133, Created)
XX
DE  XXX
XX
KW  .
XX
OS  Hordeum vulgare
XX
OC  cellular organisms; Eukaryota; Viridiplantae; Streptophyta;
OC  Streptophytina; Embryophyta; Tracheophyta; Euphyllophyta;
OC  Spermatophyta; Magnoliopsida; Mesangiospermae; Liliopsida;
OC  Petrosaviidae; commelinids; Poales; Poaceae; BOP clade;
OC  Pooideae; Triticoideae; Triticeae; Hordeinae; Hordeum
XX
RN  [1]
RP  1-257194
RG  XXX
RT  ;
RL  Submitted (13-JAN-2024) to the INSDC.
XX
FH  Key          Location/Qualifiers
FH
FT  source        1..257194
FT                /mol_type="genomic DNA"
FT                /organism="Hordeum vulgare"
FT  gene          complement(35887..40415)
FT                /locus_tag="DCAF_LOCUSSS1"
FT                /note="ID:DCAF_016137"
FT                /note="source:funannotate"
FT  mRNA          complement(join(35887..35990,38307..38442,40249..40415))
FT                /locus_tag="DCAF_LOCUSSS1"
FT                /note="ID:DCAF_016137-T1"
FT                /note="source:funannotate"
```

Assembly Data Submission: Assembly

```
ID XXX; XXX; linear; genomic DNA; XXX; XXX; XXX.
XX
AC XXX;
XX
AC * _contig_1
XX
PR Project:PRJEB71679;
XX
DT 13-JAN-2024 (Rel. 133, Created)
XX
DE XXX
XX
KW .
XX
OS Hordeum vulgare
XX
OC cellular organisms; Eukaryota; Viridiplantae; Streptophyta;
OC Streptophytina; Embryophyta; Tracheophyta; Euphyllophyta;
OC Spermatophyta; Magnoliopsida; Mesangiospermae; Liliopsida;
OC Petrosaviidae; commelinids; Poales; Poaceae; BOP clade;
OC Pooideae; Triticodae; Triticeae; Hordeinae; Hordeum
XX
RN [1]
RP 1-257194
RG XXX
RT ;
RL Submitted (13-JAN-2024) to the INSDC.
XX
FH Key Location/Qualifiers
FH
FT source 1..257194
FT /mol_type="genomic DNA"
FT /organism="Hordeum vulgare"
FT gene complement(35887..40415)
FT /locus_tag="DCAF_LOCUSS1"
FT /note="ID:DCAF_016137"
FT /note="source:funannotate"
FT mRNA complement(join(35887..35990,38307..38442,40249..40415))
FT /locus_tag="DCAF_LOCUSS1"
FT /note="ID:DCAF_016137-T1"
FT /note="source:funannotate"
```


About INSDC Global Participation Technical Specifications Publications Announcements Contact Us

The DDBJ/ENA/GenBank Feature Table Definition

The DDBJ/ENA/GenBank
Feature Table
Definition
Version 11.3 October 2024

DNA Data Bank of Japan, Mishima, Japan.
EMBL-EBI, European Nucleotide Archive, Cambridge, UK.
GenBank, NCBI, Bethesda, MD, USA.

- 1 Introduction
- 2 Overview of the Feature Table format
 - 2.1 Format Design
 - 2.2 Key aspects of this feature table design
- 2.3 Feature Table Terminology
- 3 Feature table components and format
 - 3.1 Naming conventions
 - 3.2 Feature keys
 - 3.2.1 Purpose
 - 3.2.2 Format and conventions
 - 3.2.3 Key groups and hierarchy
 - 3.2.4 Feature key examples
 - 3.3 Qualifiers
 - 3.3.1 Purpose
 - 3.3.2 Format and conventions
 - 3.3.3 Qualifier values
 - 3.3.4 Qualifier examples
 - 3.4 Location
 - 3.4.1 Purpose
 - 3.4.2 Format and conventions
 - 3.4.3 Location examples
- 4 Feature table Format
 - 4.1 Format examples
 - 4.2 Definition of line types
 - 4.3 Data item positions
 - 4.4 Use of blanks
 - 5 Examples of sequence annotation
 - 5.1 Eukaryotic gene
 - 5.2 Bacterial operon
 - 5.3 Artificial cloning vector (circular)
 - 5.4 Plasmid
 - 5.5 Repeat element

<https://www.insdc.org/submitting-standards/feature-table/>

Assembly Data Submission

Webin Reports API

Webin Reports Service ¹ OAS3

</ena/submit/report/v3/api-docs>

Webin Reports Service

Servers

[/ena/submit/report](#) ▾

Authorize

unsubmitted-files-controller ^

GET /unsubmitted-files ▾

study-controller ^

GET /studies ▾

GET /studies/{id} ▾

GET /studies/xml/{ids} ▾

Summary

<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/>

- The ENA provides **scientific record** of sequencing data.
- Established in the early 1980s, extended for **new technologies and applications**.
- Comprehensive record of world's **nucleotide sequencing information** covering raw read data, sequence assembly information and functional annotation.
- Presents large amounts of a diverse range of data in a consistent manner, making use of **data and metadata Models**.
- Metadata model requires minimal mandatory metadata in line with **FAIR data principles**.
- Rich submission, discovery and retrieval **software, tools and services**.
- **Support** through Helpdesk and training.
- **Data submission** routes: Interactive, programmatic and Webin-CLI.
- **Genome assembly data** submission with Webin-CLI using manifest files and the command line.
- **Data coordination** including project-specific data hubs and portals.

Handy links

- ENA Browser: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>
- ENA Submission/Retrieval Guide: <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/general-guide.html>
- ENA Helpdesk: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/support>
- Advanced Search: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/advanced-search>
- Webin Reports API: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/report/swagger-ui/index.html>
- Webin Portal: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>
- Webin TEST Portal: <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

**Thank you
Any Questions?**

Assembly Data Submission Practical

During this exercise, you will implement some of the skills you have just learnt and submit some assembly data to the ENA.

1. Register a study interactively
2. Register your sample using a spreadsheet
3. Submit runs with Webin-CLI using command line
4. Submit an annotated assembly with Webin-CLI using command line

Thank you
Any Questions?

